

Influence of Parental Occupation on the Entrepreneurial Intention among Commerce Students

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Abstract:- India with diversified culture and tradition experience changes in all field, education is not an exception. With the changing educational policies, and pattern of education in both school and college made people to think in global scenario. Education is the one of the platforms to remove unemployment problem and also can provide employability skills among the young generation. On this ground the researchers have made an attempt to study the level of influence of factors contributing to the entrepreneurial intention among commerce students. A sample of 120 women students who are pursuing their under graduate and post graduate in commerce, in a city women college. In recent times colleges started realizing the importance of entrepreneurial skill among their students. The data were collected through a standardized questionnaire with the help of Google form. This study validated the different factors such as entrepreneurial education, self efficacy, parent's occupation and college environment on the entrepreneurial intention of the women commerce students. The results proved that there is an influence of the entrepreneurial education, self efficacy, parent's occupation and college environment on their entrepreneurial intention. The findings of the study will definitely provide insights and inputs for the policy makers and educational institutions to frame a suitable policies and pedagogical interventions.

Keywords:- *Entrepreneurial Education, Entrepreneurial Intention, Self Efficacy, Parent's Occupation.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The thought of the younger generation is entirely different from what we conceive. Especially the entrepreneurs' children want to get employed rather than continuing with the family business nor to be an entrepreneur. This may due to various factors both economical and financial. On this ground the researchers have made an attempt to study the level of influence of entrepreneurial education, self efficacy, parent's occupation and college environment on the entrepreneurial intention of the women commerce students. "Entrepreneurship Education (EE) defined as entrepreneurship education in the subjects in college that teaches the theory and practice of entrepreneurship with the aim of students have the ability in understanding and practicing entrepreneurship, causing changes in attitudes, norms and

behavior" (Adhitya Ginanjar,2016). Most of the parents sending their children to college with the dream of making them a professionals such as accountants, managers and the like. But it is important to understand the intention of the female students that really they want to go for a job or want to become a professional or to become an entrepreneur. It is not compulsory that just because of their parents into business the students also wants to start up their business, but with the observation and by passion they want to become an entrepreneur.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Adhitya Ginanjar, 2016 conducted a case study on Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Intention on Entrepreneurship Behavior. This study elaborated the entrepreneurship education experience in Sharia Banking Program that combined the theory and the practice in one semester. The study also compared the secondary data obtained from the development of teaching. The study confirmed that an increased in the creation of entrepreneurial intention. And also suggested that the education can be one important variable in the creation of entrepreneur through higher education.

Effect of Entrepreneurship Education and Self Efficacy towards the Intention of Entrepreneurship, was examined by 2018, 2018. This study examined the description of entrepreneurship education variables and its influence on entrepreneurial intentions. It is a quantitative research conducted among 140 Grade XII, Vocational Schools. Structured questionnaire method was followed to collect primary data. The results proved that entrepreneurship education and self efficacy had a significant influence on students' intention of entrepreneurial skills. This shows that at the young age, the students can be motivated to become entrepreneurs with entrepreneurial education, make them job providers rather than job seekers. (Patricia Martyajuarlinda, 2018)

Xianyue Liue, et.al., conducted a research on the effects of Entrepreneurial Education and Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy on college students' Entrepreneurial Intention, 2019. The aim of this research was to analyzes the effect of college students' entrepreneurship education and self efficacy on their entrepreneurial intention. It is an empirical research, comprised of 327 college students in china. The outcomes of

the research were that the college students’ entrepreneurial education had a significant positive effect on their entrepreneurial intention and their entrepreneurial attitude which plays a partial intermediary role in the relationship between entrepreneurial self efficacy and entrepreneurial intention. Convenient sampling technique was used instead of random sampling and the students are from same college. Thus, the result cannot be generalized. The research can be expanded to cross region across countries. The students community comprises of different culture, social norms, economic background, linguistic differences, etc., which may affect the sample selection. Therefore this research has only theoretical significance.

Entrepreneurial self-efficacy: A systematic review of the literature on its theoretical foundations, measurement, antecedents, and outcomes, and an agenda for future research was examined by Alexander Newmana, Martin Obschonkab , Susan Schwarzc , Michael Cohena , Ingrid Nielsena , 2019. The objectives of the study were to have systematic review of the literature on the theoretical bases, measurement, antecedents, and outcomes of Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy, which treats ESE as a moderating factor. In depth reviews from various articles, journals magazines and literary works from the year 1998 till 2017 were considered as the base for this study. It is an empirical literature contribution to the research world. The outcomes of the study are ESE is entrepreneurial intention, defined as the intention of an individual to start a new business. It says ESE captures an individual’s perceptions that they are able to handle given situations (PBC). Since it is an empirical research based on past literary works, it cannot be generalized for the current changing scenario.

III. METHODOLOGY

The present study attempted to examine the influence of entrepreneurial education, self efficacy, parent’s occupation and college environment on the entrepreneurial intention of the women commerce students. A structured and standardized questionnaire was used to explore the different influencing factors such as entrepreneurial education, self efficacy and family’s business background on intention for entrepreneurship amongst female commerce students. The primary data was collected during the month of January 2022 from 120 final years under graduate and post graduate women commerce students from a renowned college in Chennai. The five point likert scale was used to measure the dependent variable, Entrepreneurial intention and independent variables such as entrepreneurial education, self efficacy, college environment and family’s business background.

IV. FINDINGS, DISCUSSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Entrepreneurial Intention refers to the an individual’s conviction to make preparations for a new business and actually follow through on this goal (Krueger et al.,2000). The impact on Entrepreneurial Intention is measured by using three other factors such as Entrepreneurial Education, Self Efficacy and College Environment. In which Entrepreneurial Intention consists of seven statements, Entrepreneurial Education consists of six statements, Self Efficacy consists of four statements and College Environment consists of five statements on a five point likert scale ranging from strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree for which the results of weighted mean and stand deviation are shown in the below table.

Table 1: Mean and SD of the Factors influencing Entrepreneurial Intention of the students based on their Parent’s Occupation

Factors	Yes		No	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Entrepreneurial Education	3.98	0.81	2.67	0.77
Self Efficacy	4.14	0.63	3.56	0.82
Entrepreneurial Intention	3.89	0.72	2.66	0.68
College Environment	4.13	0.67	2.93	0.99

From the above table it is inferred that the respondents whose parents are Entrepreneurs are having high mean and SD of Self Efficacy (4.14, 0.63) and Entrepreneurial Intention (3.89, 0.72). it is evident from the above table that the Entrepreneurial Intention for the employed parents’ children have the weighted mean score 2.66, followed by Entrepreneurial Education 2.67, College Environment 2.93 and Self Efficacy 3.56. thus the respondents have expressed their high level of Entrepreneurial Intention to become an entrepreneur even though their Self-Efficacy is low compared to other three factors. Thus it can be concluded that the factor entrepreneurial intention for the children of entrepreneurs to high to children of employed. In order to make it more confirm the researchers have applied the cross tabulation between the students’ entrepreneurial intention and their parents’ occupation. The table no..... below reveals that 56.8% of the students are interested to become entrepreneurs whose parents’ are also into business. Thus it is proved that the students are having high level of intention to become entrepreneurs instead of going for a job may be because of the influence by the parents, family business environment, their business surroundings and the like.

Table2: Association between the students who are interested in becoming entrepreneur with their parent’s occupation

Interested in becoming an Entrepreneur	Parents into Business	
	Yes	No
Yes	42 (56.8%) [85.7%]	32 (43.2%) [45.1%]
No	7 (15.2%) [14.3%]	39 (84.8%) [54.9%]
Total	49 (40.8%) [100.0%]	71 (59.2%) [100.0%]

The primary data was collected and segregated based on their parent’s occupation belonging to entrepreneurs and employed respectively. The main objective of the research is to identify whether the children of entrepreneurs are willing to take up entrepreneurship in future, which is known as entrepreneurial intention compared to children of employed parents with the factors entrepreneurial education, self-efficacy and conducive college environment motivating entrepreneurial activities. SEM was performed with the categories of students whose parents are entrepreneurs. This model reveals that the entrepreneurial intension of students whose parents are entrepreneurs.

The EE, CE and SE on EI Model was evaluated using through goodness of fit indices to check whether the factors represent the respective latent variables taken for the study. Structural Equation Model relies on several statistical tests to determine the adequacy of the model fit to the data. The factors influencing the Entrepreneurial Intention of the college students through Entrepreneurial Education, College Environment and Self Efficacy. The SEM depicting the relationships and the path coefficients are shown in Figure No.1.

**Fig 1: Entrepreneurial Intention of Entrepreneurs’ Children
The EE, CE and SE on EI Model**

Table No.3: Regression Weights : The results of Structural Equation Path Estimates

Variables			standardized Coefficient (Beta)	S.E. Of B	Un-standardized Coefficient (Beta)	t value	P
EI1	<---	EI	1.000		0.706		<0.001**
EI2	<---	EI	1.068	0.202	0.796	5.284	<0.001**
EI3	<---	EI	1.223	0.224	0.822	5.451	<0.001**
EI4	<---	EI	1.140	0.274	0.625	4.162	<0.001**
EI5	<---	EI	1.122	0.222	0.760	5.048	<0.001**
EI6	<---	EI	0.859	0.201	0.643	4.284	<0.001**
EI7	<---	EI	1.137	0.254	0.672	4.474	<0.001**
EE1	<---	EE	1.000	0.142	0.839	7.037	<0.001**
EE2	<---	EE	0.741	0.102	0.829	7.298	<0.001**
EE3	<---	EE	0.608	0.115	0.685	5.261	<0.001**
EE4	<---	EE	0.863	0.126	0.823	6.828	<0.001**
EE5	<---	EE	0.754	0.120	0.778	6.279	<0.001**
EE6	<---	EE	0.551	0.152	0.506	3.627	<0.001**
SE1	<---	SE	1.000		0.705		<0.001**
SE2	<---	SE	1.416	0.329	0.720	4.305	<0.001**
SE3	<---	SE	1.203	0.286	0.700	4.206	<0.001**
SE4	<---	SE	0.914	0.225	0.671	4.058	<0.001**
CE1	<---	CE	0.905	0.140	0.770	6.471	<0.001**

Variables			standardized Coefficient (Beta)	S.E. Of B	Un-standardized Coefficient (Beta)	t value	P
CE2	<---	CE	0.911	0.138	0.781	6.613	<0.001**
CE3	<---	CE	1.072	0.116	0.944	9.222	<0.001**
CE4	<---	CE	1.072	0.118	0.936	9.066	<0.001**
CE5	<---	CE	1.000		0.844		<0.001**
SE	<---	EE	0.351	0.092	0.693	3.826	<0.001**
CE	<---	EE	0.574	0.124	0.684	4.628	<0.001**
EI	<---	EE	0.228	0.101	0.373	2.264	0.024*
EI	<---	SE	0.341	0.174	0.284	1.961	0.050
EI	<---	CE	0.317	0.097	0.436	3.285	<0.001**

The null hypothesis no.1 states that EE has no significant and positive influence on EI of the children of entrepreneurs. From the results it is inferred that null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance since the P value is 0.024 and the critical ratio is 2.264. thus the alternate prediction that EE has a significance and positive influence on EI of the children of entrepreneurs. The effect of EE on EI with the regression weight of 0.228 implies that for every one unit increase in EE, EI increases by 0.228. thus the results indicate that EE with Beta value of 0.373 has a high influence on EI of the children of entrepreneurs.

The null hypothesis no.2 states that SE has no significant and positive influence on EI of the children of entrepreneurs. From the results it is inferred that null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance since the P value is 0.050 and the critical ratio is 1.961. Thus, the alternate prediction that SE has a significance and positive influence on EI of the children of entrepreneurs. The effect of SE on EI with the regression weight of 0.341 implies that for every one unit increase in SE, EI increases by 0.341. thus the results indicate that SE with Beta value of 0.284 has a high influence on EI of the children of entrepreneurs.

The null hypothesis no.3 states that CE has no significant and positive influence on EI of the children of entrepreneurs. From the results it is inferred that null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance since the P value is less than 0.001 and the critical ratio is 3.285. Thus, the alternate prediction that CE has a significance and positive influence on EI of the children of entrepreneurs. The effect of CE on EI with the regression weight of 0.373 implies that for every one unit increase in CE, EI increases by 3.285. thus the results indicate that CE with Beta value of 0.436 has a high influence on EI of the children of entrepreneurs.

The null hypothesis no.4 states that EE has no significant and positive influence on CE. From the results it is inferred that null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level of significance since the P value is less than 0.001 and the critical ratio is 4.628. Thus, the alternate prediction that EE has a significance and positive influence on CE. The effect of EE on CE with the regression

weight of 0.574 implies that for every one unit increase in EE, CE increases by 0.574. thus the results indicate that EE with Beta value of 0.684 has a high influence on CE.

The null hypothesis no.5 states that EE has no significant and positive influence on SE. From the results it is inferred that null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level of significance since the P value is less than 0.001 and the critical ratio is 3.826. Thus, the alternate prediction that EE has a significance and positive influence on SE. The effect of EE on SE with the regression weight of 0.351 implies that for every one unit increase in EE, SE increases by 0.351. thus the results indicate that EE with Beta value of 0.693 has a high influence on SE.

Thus the testing of 5 hypotheses reveal that the factors of the model EE, CE and SE on EI Model are significantly interrelated. The fit indices of the model are depicted in the table no 4 below.

Table 4: Model Fit Summary of Structural Equation Model

Indices	Value	Suggested value
Chi-square value	429.395	-
DF	204	-
P value	<0.001**	> 0.05 (Hair et al., 1998)
Chi-square value/DF	2.105	< 5.00 (Hair et al., 1998)
GFI	0.960	> 0.90 (Hu and Bentler, 1999)
AGFI	0.944	> 0.90 (Hair et al. 2006)
NFI	0.954	> 0.90 (Hu and Bentler, 1999)
CFI	0.944	> 0.90 (Daire et al., 2008)
RMR	0.060	< 0.08 (Hair et al. 2006)
RMSEA	0.052	< 0.08 (Hair et al. 2006)

Table no.4 reveals the standardized equation results from the testing the model. The indices were obtained from the analysis of the SEM. The study results reveal that perfect fit is indicated between the data and the causal model. the chi-square

value is less than 5 indicating the perfect fit. Goodness of fit indices should be equal to or greater than 0.90 to indicate the good fit. The value of 1 indicates perfect fit.

Thus the GFI of the model has been established from these values of GFI (0.960), AGFI (0.944), CFI (0.944), RMR (0.060), NFI (0.954) and RMSEA (0.052) indicating that the proposed conceptual model fit is perfect in this research.

All the four factors contributing to the entrepreneurial intention of entrepreneurs' children are significant because they have the ability to identify the business opportunities enhance their creativity and solve the problems through their life pattern. In addition to the above features the college environment is facilitating them to come up with their innovative ideas and convert them into a business venture. The higher educational institutions can have a focus on the students whom parents are entrepreneurs, to bringing their entrepreneurial skills up. They can be asked to come up with the business proposals which can be derived out of the experience that they gained out their parent's business. It will definitely be a motivation and a practice for them to do a design thinking and idea generation.

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